

POSSIBILITIES OF COMPREHENSIVE PROCESSING OF MAN-MADE WASTE FROM COPPER PROCESSING PLANTS

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Abstract. *Currently in the world effective methods are being developed for processing mineral raw materials and industrial waste, completely extracting valuable components and increasing production capacity for the extraction of non-ferrous and precious metals, creating low-waste and non-waste technologies. This article presents the results of research on the development of effective methods for processing technogenic tailings with high recovery of valuable components. In addition, the results of experiments on processing waste from copper concentration factories and their granulometric, mineralogical and chemical compositions are presented. Storing this waste involves large material costs and at the same time causes some damage to the environment. It is important that the ability to separate iron minerals by the electromagnetic method has increased due to the fact that the amount of iron has increased several times after the extraction of silicon dioxide from waste from copper processing plants. Thanks to this, this type of waste serves as an additional source for the extraction of iron, gold, silver, copper and other valuable components. As a result of research, the developed technology for processing technogenic waste from a copper processing plant is effectively disposed of as a result of factors such as hermetically sealed at low temperatures, environmental safety, and energy efficiency, which makes it possible to effectively process waste from copper processing plants.*

Keywords: *ore, concentrate, flotation, tailings, leaching, solution, cake, crushing, grinding, physical and chemical properties.*

Introduction

Today, it is important in the world to develop effective methods for processing mineral raw materials and polymetallic ores, to completely extract useful minerals from them, to increase the production capacity of rare and precious metals, to create low-waste and waste-free technologies. And also the involvement in the production of all types of man-made waste of the mining and metallurgical industry (waste from the mining industry, beneficiation plants, liquid and solid waste from hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical processes), the separation of silicate compounds of complex composition into individual oxides by returning the used reagents to the process, and, as a result, ensuring the extraction of useful components from the composition of man-made waste are urgent problems in this area. The technology for extracting useful components from ores is selected depending on the chemical nature of the ore being processed, in particular, copper ores are enriched mainly by the flotation method. The concentrate yield is 3-4 percent. 96-97% of the mined ore is considered waste (hosts) and is sent to the tailings dump. Currently, as a result of long-term processing of ores, the average amount of copper in two tailings dumps of Almalyk

Mining and Metallurgical Plant is 0.11%, 1459.5 million tons of man-made waste have accumulated. The total reserves of precious metals have been calculated taking into account the waste accumulated in the tailings dumps over many years, the results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

The amount of waste and metals in them accumulated up to 2024

Tailings storage facility №	Amount of accumulated waste, thousand tons.	Number of metals					
		Copper		Gold		Silver	
		%	Thousand tons	y/t	t	y/t	T
1	573000	0,112	641,7	0,29	166,17	3,06	1753,38
2	886500	0,104	921,96	0,31	274,81	2,94	2606,31
Total	1 459 500	0,11	1563,66	0,3	440,98	3	4359,69

Table 2 presents the results of chemical analysis of samples accumulated over many years. From the data provided it follows that the obtained samples are characterized by a typical aluminosilicate: 67.31% SiO₂ and 13.26% Al₂O₃.

Table 2

Complete chemical composition of samples of man-made waste

Oxides and elements	Compound, %	Oxides and elements	Compound, %
SiO ₂	67,3	S _{SO3}	0,41
Fe _{general}	8,69	SO ₂	0,90
Fe ₂ O ₃	8,83	P ₂ O ₅	0,17
FeO	3,23	±H ₂ O	0,49
TiO ₂	0,36	Cu	0,11
MnO	0,08	Pb	0,018
Al ₂ O ₃	11,57	Zn	0,026
CaO	1,30	As	0,0028
MgO	1,97	Sb	-
K ₂ O	4,27	Mo	0,0030
Na ₂ O	0,44	Au, y/t	0,3
S _{general}	2,77	Ag, r/T	3,0
S	2,36	Others	0,34

The sample taken from the waste of Almalyk KMK MBF has a sulfide content of 2.36%. The fractional composition of the waste and the distribution of metals by size fractions were also studied, the results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 shows that a large proportion of precious metals (more than 80%) falls on the +0.1 fraction, which is explained by the fact that the elements contained in large quartz minerals remain in the tailings of flotation enrichment of copper ores.

Aluminum and silicon oxides make up the bulk of the waste from copper processing plants and are contained as follows: 67.31% SiO₂ and 11.57% Al₂O₃. If, during waste processing, the main attention is paid to the separation of FeO, SiO₂ and Al₂O₃, the amount of valuable metals in dealuminosilicate waste will increase several times. This creates the possibility of complex waste processing without waste.

Table 3

Fractional composition of copper processing plant waste and distribution of metals in it

Size class, mm	Fraction output		Copper			Gold			Silver		
			Content, %	Mass, g	Distribution, %	content, g/t	Mass, g	Distribution, %	Content, r/t	Mass, g	Distribution, %
	g	%									
+ 0,59	108	5,4	0,127	0,137	6,22	0,36	0,000039	6,5	3,62	0,00039	0,65
-0,59+0,3	648,8	32,44	0,112	0,726	33,0	0,34	0,00022	36,66	3,42	0,0222	37,0
-0,3+0,21	514	25,7	0,111	0,570	25,9	0,31	0,000159	26,5	3,28	0,0168	28,0
-0,21+0,15	274	13,70	0,109	0,298	13,58	0,30	0,000082	13,6	3,17	0,00868	14,46
-0,15+0,10	84,8	4,24	0,108	0,091	4,13	0,29	0,000024	4,0	2,95	0,0025	4,16
-0,10 +0,074	77,2	3,86	0,106	0,081	3,68	0,27	0,000021	3,5	2,86	0,0022	3,66
-0,074 +0,044	149,6	7,48	0,102	0,152	6,9	0,24	0,000036	6,0	2,75	0,00411	6,85
-0,044	143,6	7,18	0,101	0,145	6,59	0,13	0,000019	3,24	2,17	0,00312	5,1
Bcero:	2000	100	0,11	2,2	100	0,3	0,0006	100	3,0	0,06	100

Based on this, the technology for processing technogenic waste using ammonium halides (NH₄F) was chosen. The following reaction mainly occurs.

Ammonium hexafluorosilicate obtained by reaction 1 has technologically advantageous physicochemical properties. This substance is solid under normal conditions, and at temperatures above 320 °C it sublimates and passes into the gas phase. Another advantage of using ammonium fluoride as a desilication reagent is the possibility of its regeneration. At a temperature of 70 °C, the solubility of ammonium hexafluorosilicate reaches 370 g/l. HFSA (ammonium hexafluorosilicate) reacts with ammonia, causing the precipitation of SiO₂.

The possibility of ammonium fluoride regeneration ensures a continuous cycle of desilication and quartz extraction from waste in the form of SiO₂ with small particles. After filtering silicon oxide from the solution, ammonium fluoride remains in the solution, and after evaporative crystallization it is returned to the waste desilication process. In order to extract useful components from the composition of technogenic waste of copper processing plants, it is first necessary to extract silicon oxide and iron oxides. For this purpose, a technological process for desilication of waste enrichment residues using ammonium halides (NH₄F or NH₄F·HF) was developed. Fig. 1 shows the cycle of desilication of technogenic waste using ammonium fluoride.

Figure 1. Scheme of the desilication cycle of industrial waste using ammonium fluoride

In order to determine the optimal parameters of sublimation roasting of copper processing plant waste, the dependence of various factors on the release of SiO₂ into an amorphous product was studied. First, the dependence of the sublimation roasting temperature on the degree of SiO₂ extraction was studied. Experiments were carried out in the temperature range from 100 °C to 500 °C for 1 hour. The constructed diagram of dependencies based on the results of the study is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Graph of the dependence of the degree of SiO₂ extraction from copper processing plant waste on the sublimation temperature

As can be seen from the diagram in Fig. 2, with an increase in the temperature of sublimation roasting of copper processing plant waste for 1 hour, the degree of SiO₂ extraction increases and reaches a high value of 75% at 450 °C, further increase in temperature does not lead to a significant increase in the degree of SiO₂ extraction. Based on this, the optimal temperature of sublimation roasting can be taken as 450 °C. Also, at the optimal temperature of 450 °C, the dependence of the degree of SiO₂ extraction on the time of sublimation roasting was studied. The experiments were carried out in the time interval from 0.5 to 3 hours. The constructed diagram of dependencies based on the results of the study is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Graph of the dependence of the degree of SiO₂ extraction from copper processing plant waste on the duration of sublimation roasting at optimal temperatures

As can be seen from the diagram in Fig. 3, the degree of SiO₂ extraction increases with the increase in the roasting time of copper processing plant waste at a temperature of 450 °C and reaches a high value of 99.77% in 120 minutes; further prolongation of the roasting time does not lead to an increase in SiO₂ extraction. Based on this, the optimal duration of sublimation roasting can be considered 2 hours. To isolate SiO₂ from the HFSA composition obtained as a result of sublimation roasting, it was treated with ammonia water (NH₄OH). Experiments were carried out with 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12% NH₄OH solutions. As a result of the studies, it was found that the optimal concentration of NH₄OH for the extraction of SiO₂ from the HFSA composition is a 10% solution. One of the advantages of isolating SiO₂ from the HFSA composition with ammonia water is the possibility of obtaining NH₄OH required for the process by absorbing ammonia gases formed during sublimation roasting of copper processing plant waste using NH₄F.

CONCLUSION

Thus, NH₄F obtained by evaporative crystallization after the release of SiO₂ is returned to sublimation roasting. This allows the desilication process to be carried out continuously and to extract finely dispersed silicon oxide from waste in the form of a white powder with a purity of 99.9.

Due to the fact that the main part of copper processing plant waste is silicon oxide (67.31% SiO₂), if the main attention is paid to the release of SiO₂, the amount of precious metals in desilicate waste will increase several times and it becomes possible to effectively extract non-ferrous and precious metals.

In order to remove SiO₂ from copper processing plant waste, the following optimal parameters of sublimation roasting with the addition of NH₄F were determined: sublimation roasting temperature – 450°C, roasting time - 2 hours, optimal concentration of NH₄OH during leaching of HFSA - 10%. The degree of SiO₂ extraction reaches 99.77%, and SiO₂ with a purity of 99.9% is obtained.

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